

INTERTEXTUALITY AND ITS TYPES

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqola notiqlik san'ati va notiq nutqini boyituvchi, ta'sirchanligi va bo'yoqdorligini oshiruvchi vositalar haqida fikr yuritiladi. Bundan tashqari, maqolada omma oldida nutq so'zlash jarayonida mashhur shaxslar, siyosatchi diplomatlar yoki buyuk olimlar bildirgan fikrlardan, hikmatli so'zlar, iboralardan foydalanish haqida gap boradi.

Kalit so'zlar. Intertekstuallik, notiqlik, nutq, ma'no, tarjima.

Annotation. This article discusses the art of oratory and the tools that enrich the speaker's speech, increase its effectiveness and colourfulness. In addition, the article gives some information about the use of quotations, idioms, phrases expressed by famous people, politicians, diplomats or great scientists while making the public speaking.

Key words. Intertextuality, public speaking, speech, meaning, translation.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются ораторского искусства и средства, обогащающие речь оратора, повышающие ее результативность и красочность. Кроме того, в статье дается информация об использовании цитат, идиом, фраз, высказанных известными людьми, политиками, дипломатами или великими учеными при публичном выступлении.

Ключевые слова. Интертекстуальность, публичное выступление, речь, смысл, перевод.

Intertextuality refers to the interdependence of texts in relation to one another (as well as to the culture at large). Texts can influence, derive from, parody, reference, quote, contrast with, build on, draw from, or even inspire each other. Intertextuality produces meaning. Knowledge does not exist in a vacuum, and neither does literature.¹

The term "intertextuality" has a wide meaning in linguistics. It refers to the literary connection between old and new works. At first, all writers become reader. They get ideas, motivation from other literary works whether this work in the same genre with his or not. If writer influences from that work, the author may imitate, use prosody, citation or quotation of his influenced work. Because, as theorist Julia Kristeva mentioned "no literary work stands entirely alone". According to her theory, every text is actually an "intertext" that exists as an intersection between other literary works².

¹ <https://www.thoughtco.com/what-is-intertextuality-1691077>

² <https://study.com/academy/lesson/intertextuality-in-literature-definition-examples.html>

Intertextuality is widely used in literature, public speaking, film making and other branches of social life.

There are nine types of intertextuality.

Allusion- An allusion is an indirect reference to another work, often by mentioning something about its main characters, themes or imagery in a way that most audiences will recognize.

Quotation- a quotation is the direct inclusion of words from one text in another text, usually in quotation marks. Quotations can also be used as titles of other works.

Calque- Calque is a linguistic term for directly translated loanwords. It is possible to use calque as a form of subtle intertextuality, but the term is more common in linguistics than in literature.

Homage- An homage is an explicit celebration of, and extended reference to, another work, writer or personage. Homages are usually impossible to miss; they are deliberate and highly expressive forms of intertextuality.

Plagiarism- Plagiarism is the process by which a writer steals someone else's work and attempts to pass it off as their own. While plagiarism is technically a form of intertextuality. It is heavily frowned upon and is considered to be intellectual and creative dishonesty.

Translation- the act of translating a work from one language to another is more than just a technical practice; it is also a creative one that is necessarily intertextual in nature, creating a cultural and linguistic interplay between the two versions of work.

Pastiche-a pastiche is a deliberate stylistic interpretation of another work or type of work. A writer deliberately imitating 19th-century literary voices while writing 21st century is creating a pastiche.

Parody- parody is a term for humorous approaches to intertextuality. Parodies often exaggerate and satirize elements of work to make a point.

Reimagining-some forms of intertextuality create sweeping reimagining of existing works. Rewriting an existing work from the perspective of a different character, for instance, would fall into this category³.

Each type of intertextuality has its own function, and according to their responsibility, they differ from each other. Some of them helps writer to appropriate or rewrite the old version to new one, some of them helps to imitate, do parody. Allusion and quotation aim indirect and direct reference to other writer's masterpiece.

As a conclusion, the aim of applying intertextuality in public speaking, literature and other sphere is to enrich our speech, define the meaning, makes beautiful scene and increase sensitivity and colourability of the work.

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